

Introduction of INUSphere^{se}

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Dear Editor,

Since I had introduced and established the therapeutic plasma exchange in 1979, later the immunoabsorption and other methods in the Nephrology Department of the University Clinic of Saarland, Homburg, Germany, I am very interested in the Therapeutic Apheresis (TA). I presented the results on various national and international congresses over different years, published them, and wrote reviews of these blood purification methods [1]. I was always surprised by the results after some TA treatments in combination with the immunosuppressive or other necessary drug therapy in patients.

Some months ago, I met an old friend, Richard Straube, MD, who has been the chief physician of the clinic in Cham, Bavaria, Germany. I want to introduce his new INUSphere^{se}-concept, which is based on a new therapy concept of the double membrane filtration method with the second hollow fiber membrane TKM58, which Richard Straube adapted to a new hardware system some years ago [2-5]. This INUSphere^{se}-concept can eliminate immunocomplexes, inflammatory mediators, and other toxic substances, and especially microplastics, from the blood. The patients with severe diseases

can be stabilized and improved under this treatment, after only a few treatments. The INUSphere^{se}-concept is more successful than the therapeutic plasma exchange method. Especially, the elimination of microplastics from blood is important today and in the future. Richard Straube can present a manuscript with graphics of eliminated microplastics, which were found in the blood of treated patients and analyzed from the TKM Sub Health Laboratory GmbH, INUS Medical Center, Cham, Bavaria, Germany.

The INUSphere^{se}-concept, as a further developed double filtration plasmapheresis system with the second hollow fiber TKM58, consists of polymer, is used successfully over several years in different diseases, such as environmental-, autoimmune-, inflammatory-, dermatological-, cancer-, long COVID diseases, and others [6]. The modified double membrane filtration system is used in Germany, in different European countries, and in some Asian countries of Asia. The advantages are high effectiveness and a low rate of side effects. Only some treatments are necessary to stabilize or improve the patients.

INUSphere^{se} is a whole new medical concept which is superior to other TA methods and has

more advantages, such as effectiveness, low side effects, to improve different severe diseases, etc. This new double filtration plasmapheresis system with immunosuppressive or other necessary drug therapy is very successful in the treatment of severe diseases. Especially, the elimination of microplastics from the blood of patients with the INUSphere® is high and very effective. Therefore, the INUSphere® can be recommended as treatment for diseases that are untreatable with conservative therapy. The INUSphere concept is carried out in specialized hospitals and private practices.

References

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